

THE BABRAHAM INSTITUTE

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In 2018-2019, there were 165 higher education institutions (HEIs) in the UK. A report on a survey by Universities UK (UUK)¹ in 2019 found that 81% of HEIs had recently provided improved support for student reporting. In June 2021, campaign group 'Reclaim the Campus'² published a report examining policies on sexual harassment at 40 UK universities, finding that only 13 of the universities had specific sexual misconduct policies. As there is no current legislation focused on GBV for the higher education (HE) sector, a voluntary approach is in place for institutions to implement guidance in the form of policies and recommendations for change.

The Equality Act 2010 drove the implementation of some policies for people with 'protected characteristics', which include sex, sexual orientation, and gender reassignment. More recently, the Office for Students (OfS) – the regulator for HE in England – published a 'Statement of Expectations',³ which is designed to provide a 'set of consistent recommendations to support higher education providers ... to prevent and respond to incidents of harassment and sexual misconduct'. This Statement is not monitored or requiring of registration, and the OfS cannot intervene or provide resolution or redress related to individual student cases and complaints (which must be dealt with through universities' internal complaints and disciplinary procedures) or constitute a regulatory requirement. Nevertheless, this Statement is a cause for institutional change. Though there have been reviews of individual universities following highly publicised sexual misconduct cases, no sanctions have been imposed and there is no oversight of the implementation of recommended change.

¹ <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/topics/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/survey-demonstrates-positive-university>

² <https://www.reclaimthecampus.com/the-reclaim-report>

³ <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/advice-and-guidance/student-wellbeing-and-protection/prevent-and-address-harassment-and-sexual-misconduct/statement-of-expectations/>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The Babraham Institute has a set of **four** policies: The Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity Policy, the Harassment & Bullying Policy, the Safeguarding Policy, and the Code of Conduct. They are a mix of dedicated GBV policies and more general policies. These policies are 'owned' by the head of HR and there is an equality4success⁴ team which unites all aspects of the equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) work at the institute with an equality4success manager.

URLs

- › Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity Policy: <https://www.babraham.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-06/BI-HR-002-Equality-Diversity-and-Inclusivity-Policy.pdf>
- › Safeguarding Policy: <https://www.babraham.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-06/BI-HAS-003-Safeguarding-Policy.pdf>
- › The Harassment & Bullying Policy and the Code of Conduct are not publicly available.

Entry into force: All four policies entered into force in 2021.

TRAINING

As part of the EU-LIFE consortium,⁵ the institute is trialling 'Active Bystander' training, initially for senior staff. In addition, the EDI Policy states that the institute is committed to training workers about their rights and responsibilities under this policy through the equality and diversity training and the Dignity at Work programme. The Bullying & Harassment Policy stipulates that all new staff, research fellows (honorary), and honorary members of faculty will receive training on bullying and harassment as part of the Induction Programme. Current staff will receive refresher training every three years. Finally, the Safeguarding Policy provides that all Institute Designated Safeguarding Leads will attend relevant training (including refresher courses) with an appropriate safeguarding agency – for example, training with Cambridge and Peterborough Safeguarding Adults and Children Boards. All workers whose roles and responsibilities include contact with children, young people, and/or adults at risk (AaR), who arrange placements involving children, young people, and/or AaR, or who carry out related risk assessments will need to complete a safeguarding awareness course and familiarise themselves with materials assigned to them on the institute's (Access Group) e-Learning platform. This course must be repeated every three years. All trustees and members of senior management are required to undergo training using the institute's (Safety Media Ltd.) e-Learning system course on 'Safeguarding Children, Young People and AaR'. This course must be repeated every three years or as required. All workers will be made aware of this policy, the Institute Safeguarding Rules and Guidance, the H&S Hub page 'Safeguarding Children and Adults at Risk & Health and Safety for Under 18s', and related policies. They will be required to read this policy and sign off in the first instance, and then read and refresh (with sign off) at least every three years.

⁴ <https://www.babraham.ac.uk/about-us/e4s>

⁵ <https://eu-life.eu/>

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The four policies combined address the following **nine** forms of GBV: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, economic and financial violence, organisational violence, online violence, and other forms. Looking into the detail of each policy, the EDI Policy focuses solely on gender-based harassment while the Bullying and Harassment Policy focuses on both sexual and gender-based harassment. The Safeguarding Policy is the only policy that addresses all nine GBV forms, while the Code of Conduct addresses none specifically.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The four policies combined address **6Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and policy. While all policies address prevention and prosecution, the Bullying and Harassment Policy and the Safeguarding Policy are the only ones that address prevalence and policy. Protection is addressed in the EDI and Safeguarding policies; only the Bullying and Harassment Policy addresses provision of services.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

All four policies address all target groups, **academic staff**, **non-academic staff**, and **students**. All policies also address other groups such as visiting staff/students, visitors to the campus site, third-party contractors, differently funded staff/students, trustees, and honorary members of faculty.

Specific vulnerable groups: The four policies combined identify all vulnerable groups included in the UniSAFE mapping as well as other groups. These include international students and staff, early-career researchers, staff and students with disabilities, staff and students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ staff and students, staff with temporary contracts, new and expectant mothers. The Code of Conduct only identifies children and vulnerable adults as being more at risk of GBV. The Safeguarding Policy addresses students and staff with disabilities, student and staff with migrant and/or ethnic minority backgrounds, as well as other groups such as children and vulnerable adults. The Bullying and Harassment Policy adds to those four groups LGBTQIA+ students and staff and new and expectant mothers. The EDI Policy addresses all of these vulnerable groups.

Intersectionality addressed: No.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Bullying and Harassment Policy addresses bystanders by stating that it may be appropriate in exceptional cases to conceal the identity of witnesses. In this event, witness statements will be anonymised. Witness should be made aware, should a case proceed to a disciplinary hearing.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Bullying and Harassment Policy addresses perpetrators. Their research funding may be withdrawn if a complaint is upheld.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. The Safeguarding Policy addresses monitoring in terms of the number of cases and results of the institutional procedure. It is not specifically about gender. Section 9.10.1. stipulates that the Institute Director and the Trustee Safeguarding Lead (TSL) will be made aware of any concerns raised by: Provision of verbal updates by the Designated Safeguarding Lead (DSL) / Deputy Designated Safeguarding Lead (DDSL) to the TSL / Institute Director on a regular basis (two times per year); Provision of an annual audit report using the Annual Safeguarding Report Template in the Institute Safeguarding RaG (the DSL / DDSL will include anonymised general statistics from all areas of the Institute); ad hoc escalation of management information relating to active cases from the DSL / DDSL as required.

Evaluation: Yes. The Safeguarding Policy addresses evaluation.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Three out of the four policies set out a step-by-step institutional procedure. The EDI Policy has none, the Bullying & Harassment Policy and the Safeguarding Policy have one procedure for all while the Code of Conduct has another type of procedure, which is that members of the public can raise concerns via the complaints policy available online.⁶

Specifically:

- The Bullying & Harassment Policy specifies who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, responsible persons/units, sanctions, and other aspects.
- The Safeguarding Policy specifies who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, a timeframe, responsible persons/units, outcomes, and other aspects.
- The Code of Conduct does not specify any procedure.

Bullying & Harassment Policy

Who to contact: The policy offers three types of action: an informal complaint, mediation, and a formal complaint. In the case of an informal complaint, individuals may discuss their complaint informally with either their line manager / supervisor or other relevant stakeholders (management, HR, a union representative, and in the case of postdoctoral fellows the Postdoc Committee). The policy specifies who to contact in the event that the bullying is carried out by a person in a senior position. Students may speak to their supervisor, mentor, assessor, the HR team, graduate studies tutor, or another member of the Graduate Committee. Mediation can be used to assist in finding an informal resolution to an issue and is complementary to the first option. This method can only be used if all parties agree to it. The HR team is in charge of mediation and should be contacted. In the event that a person wishes to raise a formal complaint, they need to inform their line manager / supervisor, a senior manager, or a member of the HR team. In this case, a complaint should be raised as soon as possible after the incident(s) or after the informal process / mediation has failed.

How to report: The individual should provide details to the HR team in writing, together with any relevant documents, including the name of the person alleged to have carried out the bullying; dates / times / locations of any incidents; nature of the incidents; witnesses; and actions the individual has tried to resolve the matter informally.

The description of the investigation: An independent senior manager is appointed by the HR team to investigate the alleged incident, to establish the facts of the case, and to decide the outcome. The investigation is conducted with the support of the HR team. All investigatory meetings are carried out with strict confidentiality. The alleged perpetrator is informed of the allegations against them in writing. Both the alleged perpetrator and the complainant go through meetings with the person in charge of the investigation. They do not have a statutory right to be accompanied at the investigation meeting; however, this may be agreed upon. The investigation should be completed in a timely manner after the submission of the formal complaint. The person in charge of the investigation prepares written summaries of the meetings to be agreed and signed by the parties to those meetings. Witness statements may be anonymised. Witnesses should be made aware that should a case proceed to a disciplinary hearing, their statement will be disclosed to the alleged perpetrator. Once an investigation has been completed, a report is prepared stating the outcome.

⁶ https://www.babraham.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-01/BI-COR-009_Complaints_Policy.pdf

The report is sent to an independent senior manager who had not been involved in the case, appointed by HR, to manage the disciplinary process going forward. The senior manager makes the decision whether they agree or not with the investigation outcome and also write, if necessary, the reasons why they do not agree. The investigation report and a letter stating the outcome of the investigation are sent to both parties. If the complainant is not satisfied with the outcome of the investigation, they have the right to appeal against that decision. To do so, they need to write to the HR team within ten working days of receiving the investigation outcome letter. An appeal hearing is set up, and the complainant has the right to be accompanied by a colleague or trade union representative. Only new or additional evidence is considered, and a decision is made whether further investigation is needed. The outcome of the appeal hearing is confirmed in writing within five working days. The decision made at the appeal hearing is final.

Responsible persons/units: HR and line managers.

Sanctions: There is a disciplinary policy in place which identifies harassment as a serious disciplinary offence. In some cases, harassment may lead to summary dismissal. If it is found that there is no case to answer, the complainant may be offered help or counselling through the institute. However, if it is found that the complainant has made an unfounded or malicious or vexatious allegation, a disciplinary policy may be invoked.

Other: A procedural flowchart and a list of contacts within the institute are provided. An appeals process is also described.

Safeguarding Policy

Who to contact: To raise a concern, a person can contact a dedicated e-mail address or one of the following: The Trustee Safeguarding Lead (TSL), the Designated Safeguarding Lead (DSL), or the Deputy Designated Safeguarding Lead (DDSL). In the event that the DSL / DDSL has a conflict of interest, the TSL, Chief Operating Officer (COO), and / or Institute Director will appoint an appropriate deputy to carry out their safeguarding duties.

How to report: If an individual is unsure whether a suspected incident falls within the definition of abuse, they can first contact any Designated Safeguarding Lead to discuss their concerns.

Timeframe: An acknowledgement of receipt, including next steps, is sent by the DSL / DDSL to the person(s) raising the concern within two working days. A preliminary assessment and inquiry is to be completed within two working days by the DSL / DDSL with support from the HR team. This preliminary stage involves discussion with the relevant line manager in order to make a speedy risk assessment and agree actions.

The description of the investigation: Anyone who has suspicions and / or concerns involving harm to children, young people, and AaR must ensure that these are raised immediately. If an individual is unsure whether a suspected incident falls within the definition of abuse, they can first contact any Designated Safeguarding Lead (DSL) to discuss their concerns.

At any stage of this preliminary process the DSL / DDSL may seek the advice of the Local Authority Designated Officer or Cambridgeshire and Peterborough Multi-Agency Safeguarding Hub. A preliminary assessment and inquiry is completed within two working days by the DSL / DDSL with support from the HR team. This preliminary stage involves discussion with the relevant line manager in order to make a speedy risk assessment and agree actions. Where the individual raising a concern feels unable to involve their line / activity manager (because they are the person

about whom there is a concern), the DSL / DDSL will involve the COO in their stead. If the COO has a conflict of interest, the concern will be raised with the Institute Director or TSL, who shall appoint an appropriate deputy.

Responsible persons/units: There is a combination of teams with different roles. The primary responsible units are the Designated Safeguarding Leads, and the Designated Child Protection / Safeguarding Staff in the Nursery, Fun Pack Holiday Club (FHC) & Fun Pack After School Club (FASC).

Outcomes: If disciplinary measures are to be initiated, the disciplinary policy and procedures are activated. The DSL / DDSL plays a key role in informing the Disciplinary Panel in any safeguarding disciplinary procedure.

Other: Where the allegations concern situations that require rapid action to prevent further risk or harm to children, young people, or AaR, the DSL / DDSL takes rapid appropriate action to ensure that any such potential or actual danger or risk is prevented. This may include, in conjunction with the head of HR, suspending the respondent pending investigation. In taking such actions, the DSL / DDSL makes clear to all parties that the actions taken are not to be regarded as disciplinary action and do not in themselves indicate that the allegation is considered to be true.

If a child or young person or AaR is considered to be at risk of significant harm, the DSL / DDSL informs the COO and immediately seeks the advice of the Local Authority Designated Officer. If they deem it necessary, the Local Authority Designated Officer will lead further investigation. They may also involve the Cambridgeshire and Peterborough Multi-Agency Safeguarding Hub (MASH). The MASH is a multi-agency environment with full-time involvement from Children's Social Care, Police, Health, Education, Early Help, Domestic Abuse Services, and a number of virtual partners such as Youth Offending, Probation, Fire Service, and Housing.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Kate Clayton-Hathway in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

